

Differences in the Structural Organisation of the Two Subunits of *Escherichia coli* Ribosome*

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Various approaches that are being made in our and other laboratories to understand the overall structural organisation of the complex organelle, the 70S ribosome and its subunits 50S and 30S ribosomes, have been reviewed. Immunoelectron microscopy and neutron diffraction analysis are two of the most sophisticated techniques being employed and considerable amount of information has already been obtained with the help of these two techniques. In our laboratory simpler approaches are being made towards the understanding of the differences in the structural organisation of the two subunits. These include: (1) kinetics of degradation of ribosomes and their subunits by RNaseI and the inhibitory capacity of the 70S and 30S ribosomes towards the RNaseI catalysed hydrolysis of polyribonucleotides, (2) the binding of the intercalating and nonintercalating dyes to the ribosomes, (3) the differential effects of formaldehyde on the two subunits, (4) differential effects of putrescine and spermidine on the subunits, (5) differences in the action of trypsin and (6) immunoprecipitation of ribosomes and their subunits. These investigations clearly point out that the structure of 30S ribosome is less flexible than that of 50S ribosome; further, the 50S ribosome has an RNA-rich and protein-poor region which is most likely to be the 'L7/L12' stalk visualised by Lake and his coworkers by immunoelectron microscopy. This stalk may have an important functional role to play.

RIBOSOME, a supramolecular complex itself, is actively engaged in the complex process of protein synthesis in the cells, which involves the interaction of a hundred or so factors. Originally ribosome was thought to be an inert platform on which the amino acids are assembled into proteins in the sequence determined by the genetic material DNA and its message being passed on to the ribosome through the messenger RNA. As per jargon of Molecular Biology, the production of messenger RNA on DNA template is known as 'transcription' and the assembly of amino acids as per transcribed message leading to the synthesis of the protein is known as 'translation'. Ribosome is a translational machinery. A number of excellent reviews are available on bacterial ribosomes¹⁻⁷ with which this article is primarily concerned. No attempt will be made here to present a similar review as the object of the present article is to point out the differences in the salient features of the two subunits of *Escherichia coli* ribosome. Before dealing with the information obtained through our own work, that already available in the literature will be documented.

Historical aspects :

Historically speaking, Luria *et al.*⁸ first observed in 1943 from the electron micrographs of bacterial cell lysates obtained by the infection of bacterial cells with bacteriophages that a granular material much smaller than virus particle had come out from the bacterium along with the virus particles. Schachman *et al.*⁹ observed such particles in all bacterial species irrespective of the infection with any virus. Palade¹⁰ was the first one to detect them, in the animal cells, attached to the endoplasmic reticular structure. Subsequently those were detected in plants¹¹ and yeast¹² and it was very soon realised that they widely occur in the living system. The role of such small particles in protein synthesis was established by Littlefield *et al.*¹³ who found it as the site of initial incorporation of radioactive amino acids into proteins. Tissieres *et al.*¹⁴ isolated these particles from the exponentially growing *Escherichia coli* cells and demonstrated their structural dependence on the concentration of Mg⁺⁺ ion. The word 'ribosome' was first coined by Roberts¹⁵ in 1958 from the observation that

*I distinctly remember the early morning hours when our 'Sir' who was then only 35 years old, was ready for breakfast after waking up from his bed which was nothing but the working bench of the Physical Chemistry Laboratory of the Department of Applied Chemistry of the University of Calcutta. Myself and a friend of mine (Chitta Raha) who is settled in U.S.A., had become the real 'Chelas' of the 'Guru' by sleeping on the laboratory benches of the Bose Institute next door. Our daily adventure was to the tea-shop just outside the University College of Science and the breakfast consisted of hot 'Jilabees'. We could not afford more than that due to meagre fellowship money. Our 'Guru' earned a little more no doubt but most of his money was committed on the first day of the month, to the numerous people, some known and some unknown to him. Indeed it is a tremendous pleasure and unique honour for me to dedicate this article to my revered 'Guru' Sushil Kumar Mukherjee, Ex-Vice-chancellor of the University of Calcutta on the occasion of his sixty-fifth birthday.

those contained both ribonucleic acids and proteins. The first and last four letters of 'Ribonucleoprotein particles of microsome' constitute the name. The endoplasmic reticular structure of the animal cells become fragmented on disruption of the cell and can be sedimented at high gravitational field and the fragmented material is designated as microsome. However, no such reticular structure is found in bacteria.

Components of *E. coli* ribosome :

The most widely studied species of ribosome and the one with which our work is primarily concerned is that of the bacterium *Escherichia coli*. As shown in Fig. 1, the *E. coli* ribosome has a sedimentation

Fig. 1. Components of *Escherichia coli* ribosome

constant 70S and molecular weight of 2.7×10^6 consists of two subunits, a large 50S subunit (mol. wt. 1.85×10^6) and the smaller 30S (mol. wt. 0.85×10^6). Both 70S ribosome and its subunits contain about two-third RNA and the remaining one-third, protein. The smaller subunit contains one 16S RNA molecule (~ 1600 nucleotides; mol. wt. 5.5×10^5) and 21 different proteins. The large 50S subunit consists of two RNAs, 23S (~ 3200 nucleotides; mol. wt. 1.1×10^6) and 5S (120 nucleotides, mol. wt. 0.4×10^5) and 34 different proteins. Waller^{15a} first showed in 1964 that ribosome is made of different proteins. Most of these proteins have been isolated in pure form and their properties have been studied by physical, chemical and immunological methods. One of the proteins is found to be common to both the subunits (S20 of 30S and L26 of 50S, the numbers being assigned on the basis of the movement on polyacrylamide gel on two-dimensional electrophoresis). The molecular weights of the proteins range from 7,000-32,000 with an average molecular weight of approximately 17,000 except one 30S subunit protein S1 which has a much higher molecular weight (65,000). Divalent cations like Mg^{++} stabilize these particles. In presence of 10 mM Mg^{++} the two subunits remain associated with each other, on lowering the Mg^{++} concentration the two dissociate.

L7 and L12 of the larger subunit are identical

proteins with the only difference that in L7 N-terminal serine amino acid residue is N-acetylated. L7/L12 occur in 3 to 4 copies per ribosome^{16,17}, whereas all other proteins occur in 1 copy per ribosome. Further, L8 has been claimed to be a complex of L7/L12 and L10 and thus there may not be any unique L8 protein¹⁸.

Immunoelectronmicroscopy :

A central step towards the understanding of the structure and function of the ribosome, a large multicomponent assembly, is the elucidation of the spatial arrangement of its proteins on RNA which will lead to the understanding of the overall structural organisation of the two subunits. The topography of ribosomal components has been investigated by a number of elegant experimental approaches of which two are worth mentioning. Among these two, immunology coupled with electron microscopy has yielded the most extensive information on the spatial arrangement of proteins. The other technique is neutron diffraction; it is in its early stage of development but holds great promise in this area.

The availability of specific antibodies to each of the 54 ribosomal proteins from *E. coli* has made the electron microscopic localisation of the ribosomal proteins possible. Apart from the antisera for two protein pairs (L7 and L12 as well as S20 and L26) no immunological cross reaction has been found between the 55 different antisera raised against all the proteins of the ribosome. During the last 4 or 5 years Stoffler's group has localised all 21 ribosomal proteins on the smaller subunit surface by immunoelectron microscopy¹⁹⁻²⁵. Using the same approach several proteins on the same subunit have been localised independently by Lake's group²⁶⁻²⁹. From their studies Stoffler's group visualises 30S subunit as a quasisymmetrical object with a small head and a large body containing a hollow, the body having elongated expansion on both the sides (Fig. 2A). In contrast Lake's group visualises the 30S subunit as a completely symmetrical object with small head, large body without hollow and a quite prominent high shoulder or platform (Fig. 2B). One of the important information obtained by immunee-

Fig. 2. Proposed models of 50S and 30S ribosomes of *Escherichia coli* suggested by (A) Wittmann and his group; (B) Lake and his group.

electronmicroscopic studies is that most of the proteins extend over a greater length of the ribosome than expected from globular form³⁰. The protein S4 is a typical example of such protein³¹.

Similarly, there are two different models for the 50S subunit. This subunit is described by Stoffler's group as an apparently symmetrical object with three conspicuous protuberances that are almost symmetrically arranged around a depression at the top of the body (Fig. 2A). But Lake's group suggested that the crests are neither pronounced nor symmetrical. It remains to be seen which of the two models, if at all, turns out to be most faithful. One of the dramatic differences between the two models is in respect of localisation of L7/L12 proteins which occur in 3/4 copies in each large subunit. Stoffler's group localises those lying as a garland around the central protuberance²¹, where as Lake's group visualizes those to be located in a single region extended from the large subunit named as L7/L12 stalk which extends at an angle of 50° from one side of the central protuberance²². Naturally, a lot of more work has to be carried out to refine the models

Neutron diffraction :

The demonstration by Schoenborn *et al.*³³ that hydrogen is clearly distinguishable from all other atomic species commonly found in biological system by neutron diffraction led Engelman and Moore³⁴ to suggest that the insight into the three-dimensional structure of ribosomes can be obtained by studying their neutron scattering properties in solution. By this technique Moore *et al.*³³ found that the centres of masses of RNA and protein distributions are substantially separated and suggested an asymmetric structure for 50S subparticle. In contrast, the 30S subunit contains RNA and protein nearly uniformly distributed³⁶. By using X-ray diffraction as well as neutron scattering Serdyuk and Grenader³⁷ determined the radii of gyration of protein and RNA in 50S subunit to be 104 and 65 Å respectively, which also suggest that RNA is closer to the centre of the 50S particle than is the protein. The asymmetric distribution of RNA and protein in 50S subunit was also confirmed by Stuhmann *et al.*³⁸ but they found that the asymmetry is much less pronounced, the centres of masses of RNA and proteins being separated by a distance of 20 Å which is much less than reported by Moore *et al.*³⁵ Stuhmann *et al.*³⁹ prepared a model of 50S subunit from a series of low angle neutron scattering measurements which is in good agreement with the models determined by electron microscopy. Engelman *et al.*⁴⁰ employed this technique for measuring the separation and shape of proteins in 30S subunit. The triangular relationships involving S3, S4, S5, S7 and S8 have been completely worked out by such method⁴¹. The extension of this work and earlier results⁴² led to the construction of a three-dimensional map of the positions of the above-mentioned proteins as well

as S9. The analysis by such method is laborious and painstaking and therefore the progress is slow but it is being hoped that eventually the information will be very much useful in establishing the three-dimensional structure of the ribosome.

Action of RNase I :

Ribonuclease I (RNaseI), an enzyme occurring in the periplasmic space of the bacterium *Escherichia coli*, is known to degrade ribonucleic acid to intermediate cyclic nucleotides which eventually get hydrolysed to a mixture of 2'- and 3'- nucleotides^{43,44}. While purifying this enzyme from the extract of *Salmonella typhimurium*^{44,45}, it was observed in this laboratory that the activity of the enzyme in the extract is comparatively low and this activity increases considerably during the purification, specially after the gel filtration step. It was suspected that an inhibitor of the enzyme which was removed during purification was present in the extract. However, attempts to purify the inhibitor failed till it was realised that the inhibitor was the ribosome present in these extracts. The search through the literature showed that the enzyme RNaseI was originally reported to be a ribosomal enzyme due to its strong association with the ribosome⁴⁶, but later on Neu and Heppel⁴⁷ demonstrated that this periplasmic enzyme gets artificially associated with the smaller subunit.

The above mentioned results were confirmed in this laboratory and two interesting observations were made. The 70S ribosome inhibits the hydrolysis of polyribonucleotides (poly A being used in general) as catalysed by RNaseI. The extent of inhibition depends on the amount of ribosome and 0.005 A₂₆₀ unit of ribosome produces 50% inhibition (Fig. 2 in ref 45). When the larger ribosome (50S) is used alone no inhibition is observed at all even when excess amount is used. The smaller ribosome (30S) is a potent inhibitor and half the amount of 30S ribosome produces the same extent of inhibition as in case of 70S ribosome showing that only the 30S component is inhibitory. These results are highly reproducible and the method is being routinely used in this laboratory to check the purity of the subunit preparations. These results also clearly show that there must be some difference in the structural organisation of the two subunits, which makes one a strong inhibitor of the enzyme and the other having absolutely no effect in this respect. Apparently the larger ribosome (50S) has some RNA-rich region highly susceptible to the action of RNase I which leads to its total degradation by RNase I and thus no inhibition is observed. Actually the kinetics of degradation of 50S and 30S ribosomes^{48,49} confirmed this. Although at very low concentration of Mg⁺⁺ (or in presence of EDTA which chelates Mg⁺⁺) both the subunits are degraded at fast rates; at a Mg⁺⁺ concentration of 1 mM the 30S ribosome is not degraded at all, whereas 50S ribosome is degraded at a reasonably fast rate. This explains the absence of inhibitory

capacity of the 50S ribosome. The behaviour of 70S ribosome is more or less the same as that of 30S ribosome.

It was observed by Datta and Burma⁴⁵ that the intact structure of 70S ribosome (rather 30S ribosome) is essential for its inhibitory capacity. Even if a small amount of protein is removed from the ribosome by treatment with salt its inhibitory capacity is reduced; if substantial amount of protein is removed the capacity may be drastically decreased. This shows indirectly that 50S ribosome has protein-poor region(s) which may be the site(s) of attack by RNase I. It was subsequently observed that the kinetics of degradation of 50S ribosome can be drastically affected at high Mg^{++} concentration (10-20 mM). Actually the degradation of 50S ribosome (as well as 30S ribosome) is biphasic in nature. At high concentration of Mg^{++} the biphasic nature is also observed but after partial degradation of the ribosome (about 10%) the remaining core particles become resistant to the further attack of RNase I (ref. 49). Detailed studies indicated that four proteins L4, L7, L10 and L12 are specifically removed by the action of RNase I and 10% of RNA is lost as acid-soluble fragments. The analysis of the fragmented RNA by fingerprinting technique is being carried out to find out which segment of RNA is prone to the attack of RNase I. As already mentioned, it was suggested by Tischendorf *et al.*⁴¹ that L7/L12 are located as garland in the central protuberance of the arm-chair model proposed by them. Circumstantial evidences show that protein L10 may be located in the same region^{49a}. However, the position of L4 is not known. It was tentatively concluded from our results that this central protuberance is the site of attack. As described earlier, the model proposed by Strycharz *et al.*³² is somewhat different from that proposed by Stoffler and Wittmann⁴⁰. The former group has recently shown that L7/L12 are exclusively located in a protruded region (L7/L12 stalk) on the 50S ribosome. This region is also found to assume different orientations under different conditions. From our data it appears that this stalk region is RNA-rich and thus very much susceptible to the attack of RNase I. The results can be properly interpreted when the actual model of 50S ribosome is established.

Binding of intercalating and nonintercalating dyes :

Considerable amount of work has been carried out on the binding of intercalating dyes like ethidium bromide to ribosome⁵⁰⁻⁵². Ethidium bromide is known to intercalate in between two base pairs of DNA and thus untwist the superhelical structure of DNA⁵³. On the basis of this it has been assumed that ethidium bromide might as well intercalate in the double stranded regions of rRNAs of ribosome. It has been shown in this laboratory that the ethidium bromide-treated 70S ribosome has increased sensitivity to its degradation by RNase I⁵¹. This must be due to the unfolding of the structure of the ribosome. Ballesta *et al.*⁵² subsequently showed

that ethidium bromide causes progressive inactivation of some steps in protein synthesis by releasing L7 and L12 at lower concentration and L8, L9, L11, L27, L29 and L30 at higher concentration. Sinharay *et al.*⁵⁴ studied in this laboratory the binding of a nonintercalating dye, berenil (4,4'-diazo-amino-dibenzamidine diacetate) to the ribosome and observed structural changes induced in the ribosome, as detected by the action of RNase I. Ali and Burma⁵⁵ carried out detailed studies on the effects of treatment of the ribosome with ethidium bromide and berenil on the various steps of protein synthesis and observed that ethidium bromide treatment has drastic effect on some steps as observed by Ballesta *et al.*⁵² but berenil treatment leads to slight loss of such activities.

During the above-mentioned studies a very interesting observation was made⁴⁸. The binding of ethidium bromide to the ribosome is dependent on the concentration of Mg^{++} , at low Mg^{++} concentration (0.1 mM) the binding is maximum and the binding decreases with the increase in Mg^{++} concentration. Same is true for individual subunits of the ribosome but there is a dramatic difference in the behaviour of the two. In case of 30S ribosome the extent of binding is affected to a small extent when Mg^{++} concentration is varied almost 40-fold (0.1 mM-4 mM) whereas the binding is very much affected in case of 50S ribosome. The maximum binding is observed at 0.1 mM as is case of 30S ribosome but at 4 mM Mg^{++} there is very little binding. These data clearly indicate that there is a subtle difference in the structural organisation of the two subunits. The structure of 50S ribosome seems to be very much flexible so far as the dye binding is concerned. It is being suspected that the RNA-rich region of the subunit (as indicated by the kinetics of degradation by RNase I) is perhaps the most flexible region which in turn controls the overall structural organisation of the subunit.

Differential effects of formaldehyde :

It is well known that formaldehyde primarily reacts with the free amino groups of the bases of the nucleic acids and the amino groups of the proteins, thereby altering the structure of both the macromolecules⁵⁶. Formaldehyde treatment of the 70S ribosome leads to the 'fixing' of the subunits as indicated by the stability of protein-RNA interaction: further, no dissociation of the treated ribosome into subunits takes place even at low Mg^{++} concentration⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹. Amons and Moller⁵⁹ demonstrated that the 'fixing' was due to inter- and intramolecular protein-protein interaction rather than RNA-protein crosslinking. Sun *et al.*⁶⁰ detected a protein-protein crosslink involving protein S16 at the subunit interface as a result of mild formaldehyde treatment. However, interaction of formaldehyde with ribosome is reversible in nature and leads to a wide variety of adducts depending on the reaction condition. Eventually, Moller *et al.*⁶¹ showed that

10-15% of the total proteins remained bound to RNA under the mild condition of treatment and little or no irremovable protein-protein crosslinking was observed.

It has been observed in this laboratory⁶³ that the 70S ribosome of *E. coli* becomes resistant to the hydrolytic action of RNase I on treatment with formaldehyde ; the extent of resistance depends on the concentration of Mg^{++} during the treatment as well as during the degradation assay. At higher Mg^{++} concentrations the effect becomes more prominent perhaps due to the folding of the structure of the ribosome. But the most important finding is that the effects of formaldehyde on 30S and 50S ribosomes are somewhat different. As evident from the kinetics of degradation, the structure of smaller ribosome becomes more susceptible to the hydrolytic action of RNase I, whereas the larger ribosome becomes slightly more resistant. Apparently, the crosslinking with formaldehyde leads to the protection of rRNA regions of 50S ribosome which are amenable to the hydrolytic action of RNase I. No such protection is observed in case of the smaller subunit. Apparently its structure becomes slightly 'unfolded', may be due to the weakening of the interaction between RNA and proteins as a result of formaldehyde treatment. It has been observed that any attempt to modify either protein or RNA component of the ribosome leads to the unfolding of the structure of the ribosome^{51,54,63-68}. As mentioned already, there are some inherent differences in the structural organisation of the two subunits and this is reflected in the formaldehyde treatment as well.

Antagonistic effects of putrescine and spermidine :

Mg^{++} and spermidine have been shown to shift the equilibrium between 70S ribosomes and 50S and 30S subunits towards 70S couples^{69,70}, whereas monovalent cations⁶⁹⁻⁷¹ and initiation factors IF1 and IF3^{72,73} shift the equilibrium towards dissociation. It has been shown in our laboratory^{83,64,66} that the polycationic amines, spermidine and spermine, have similar effect as Mg^{++} on the structure of the 70S ribosome so far as the degradation of the ribosome by RNase I and the inhibition of the ribosome of RNase I catalysed hydrolysis of poly (A) are concerned. Rosano and Hurwitz⁷⁴ have reported that spermidine and putrescine have antagonistic actions on the association and dissociation of run-off ribosomes of *E. coli*. Putrescine and spermidine were found to have antagonistic effects on the structure of 70S ribosome as observed by the action of RNase I, depending on the concentration of Mg^{++} as well as the polycationic amine⁷⁵. Spermidine counteracts and putrescine facilitates the action of RNase I on the 70S ribosome. 50S and 30S ribosomes also behave similarly but the effect of putrescine is more prominent in the case of 50S ribosome at high concentration of Mg^{++} . It is not known whether this is due to more exposed regions of RNA in the

former case. Spermidine and spermine are similarly known to have greater influence on the structure of 50S ribosome.

Treatment with trypsin :

Kazi *et al.*⁷⁶ studied the effect of trypsin treatment on ribosome function and observed that the ribosome lost some of its biological functions although very little soluble material was lost. Chang and Flaks⁷⁷ and Craven and Gupta⁷⁸ using both soluble and matrix-bound trypsin showed that only those proteins of *E. coli* which enter late in the *in vitro* assembly of ribosome are sensitive to tryptic action. The results obtained by Spitnik-Elson and Breiman⁷⁹ indicated that the trypsin sensitivity of ribosomal proteins depends on their interaction with other RNAs and proteins. Gualerzi and Pon⁸⁰ showed that the trypsin treatment of 30S ribosome has very little effect on its binding with IF3. Proteolytic enzymes are also being used to find out the proteins of the ribosomal proteins interacting with rRNAs⁸¹⁻⁸². Trypsin has also been used as a probe for proteins accessibility^{79,83,84} and this has been complicated by factors such as simultaneous digestion of several proteins and the influence of RNA on the resistance of a protein to trypsin^{85,86}. In a recent paper Changchien and Craven⁸⁷ have compared the digestion patterns of the complexes of rRNAs and proteins and deduced specific protective effects of a protein on its neighbour. The tryptic action on the 70S ribosome and its subunits is being studied in this laboratory by a simple assay method using S³⁵-labelled ribosomes as substrate and determining the trichloroacetic acid-soluble radioactivity released as a result of the treatment⁸⁸. The ribosome loses phenylalanine-polymerising activity drastically on trypsin treatment although no fragments are released from the ribosome, as determined by density gradient centrifugation. The structure of 70S ribosome and its subunits is 'unfolded' on treatment with trypsin but the subunits are more susceptible to trypsin than the intact ribosome. Further, the structure of the smaller subunit is more affected than the 30S ribosome under the same condition of treatment indicating the differences in the structural organisation of the two subunits.

Immunological approaches :

As already discussed before the immunological approaches coupled with electron microscopic technique have yielded very useful information about the overall structural organisation of the ribosome and the models of the two subunits have been built on this basis. In a rather very simple approach in this laboratory^{89,90} antisera were raised in rabbits against 70S, 50S and 30S ribosomes individually and their efficiencies in the precipitation of the ribosomes and their subunits were tested. Antiserum or Immunoglobulin G (IgG) prepared from the antiserum having the maximum activity against 70S ribosome precipitates the 70S ribosome

most efficiently; the precipitation of 50S ribosome is comparatively less and that of 30S ribosome is still lower. Antiserum against 50S ribosome precipitates about 70-80% of both 70S and 50S ribosomes. Antiserum raised against 30S ribosome precipitates 70S ribosome less efficiently (70%) but 30S ribosome is precipitated to a greater extent (50-60%) than with the antiserum against 70S ribosome. The ultracentrifugation experiments corroborated the above findings. It was shown in a differently designed experiment that the presence of 50S ribosome helped in the precipitation of the 30S ribosome. These results also indicate that there is some structural difference between the two ribosomes, which is responsible for the difference in the extents of precipitation of the two subunits. Similar situation was observed by Wool and his coworkers^{91,92} with the two subunits of rat liver ribosomes.

In order to find out the effect of immunoglobulins on the structure of the ribosomes and to avoid precipitation of ribosomes, monovalent Fab fragments obtained by the digestion of immunoglobulins with papain were used⁹³. Treated ribosomes and their subunits were degraded at faster rates than the untreated ones, the rates in both the control and the treated cases being dependent on the concentration of Mg^{++} . These results indicate the unfolding of the structure of the ribosome on treatment with antibody fragments, which may be due to the weakening of the interaction between rRNAs and ribosomal proteins. The effect is found to be somewhat more pronounced in case of 30S ribosome than the 50S ribosome.

Conclusion

The challenge posed by the structure of a complicated organelle like 'ribosome' will naturally involve sophisticated approaches and considerable time for final solution. The techniques like immunoelectron-microscopy, neutron diffraction, low angle X-ray diffraction etc. are the techniques of promise, as indicated in the present review. It should, however, be emphasised that even simpler approaches sometimes may yield useful information. The methods that are being employed in this laboratory like the kinetics of degradation of ribosomes and their subunits by RNaseI, dye binding studies, immunological approaches etc. are the typical examples to cite. A salient difference in the organisation of RNAs and proteins in the two subunits has been hinted at from these studies. A definite indication of the presence of an RNA-rich and protein-poor region in 50S ribosome has thus been obtained. Structurally and functionally speaking, this observation may be of great importance. A more specific approach is necessary to understand this region to fit its structural and functional characteristics in the overall structural organisation of the larger subunit and its function in conjunction with the smaller subunit. Some of these studies are in progress.

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